

Data Pitch

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D1.2 Data Management Plan v2

Coordinator: Jennifer Gaskell

With contributions from: Johanna Walker, Laura Carmichael, Sophie Stalla-Bourdillon

Quality reviewer: Ryan Goodman

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Table of Contents

Abstract	2
Executive summary	3
1. Introduction	6
1.1 Data Pitch: brief overview	6
1.2 Objective of the Data Management Plan	6
1.3 Personal data	7
2. List of Datasets	9
2.1 Data Providers Database	9
2.2 Data Providers Legal and Technical Submissions	11
2.3 Data Providers Challenge Templates	13
2.4 Challenge Consultation	15
2.5 General Statistics on Call for Applications	17
2.6 Database of submissions	19
2.7 Evaluation and interview results	21
2.8 Non-successful applicants' email addresses	23
2.9 Records of self-supplied data	24
2.10 Statistics on startup acceleration	26
2.11 Statistics on usage of data and computing infrastructure.	28
2.12 Newsletter recipient database	33
2.13 Data Provider Contracts	32
2.14 SME Contracts, Declarations of Honour, Ethics Statement and other signed manuscripts	33
2.15 Data Providers' Metadata	35
2.16 SME Accelerator working documents	38
2.17 Accelerator training materials	40

Abstract

This deliverable reports on how data collected and generated within Data Pitch will be stored, managed and reported on. This report - Data Management Plan (DMP) v2 - is conceived as an

update to the first DMP that was delivered in M6 of the Data Pitch programme by: (i) reviewing and (if necessary) amending the information about the datasets recorded in the first version of the DMP; and (ii) adding information about any additional datasets.

Executive summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is concerned with the data generated or collected during the commission of the Data Pitch project. This report - Data Management Plan v2 - provides an update to the first DMP delivered in M6 by: (i) reviewing and (if necessary) amending the information about the datasets recorded in the first version of the DMP; and (ii) adding information about any additional

datasets.

The following table lists the datasets that are/will be generated/collected over the course of the Data Pitch programme:

Overview of datasets generated/collected over the course of the Data Pitch programme*				
	Dataset reference	Relevant work package(s)	Dataset Name	First recorded in DMP
1	DS-2A	2	Statistics on Usage of Data and Infrastructure	M6
2	DS-3A	3	Data Providers Database	M6
3	DS-3B	3	Data Providers Legal and Technical Submissions	M6
4	DS-3C	3	Data Providers Challenge Templates	M6
5	DS-3D	3	Challenge Consultation	M6
6	DS-3E	3	Data Provider Contracts	M6
7	DS-3F	3	Data Providers' Metadata	M6
8	DS-4A	4	General Statistics on Call for Applications	M6
9	DS-4B	4	Database of Submissions	M6
10	DS-4C	4	Non-Successful Applicants' Email Addresses	M19
11	DS-4D	4	Evaluation and Interview Results	M6
12	DS-4E	4	SME Contracts, Declarations of Honour, Ethics Statement and Other Signed Manuscripts	M6
13	DS-4F	4 and 5	Records of Self-Supplied Data	M19
14	DS-5A	5	Statistics on Start-up Acceleration	M6

15	DS-5B	5	SME Accelerator Working Documents	M19
16	DS-5C	5 and 6	Accelerator Training Materials	M19
17	DS-6A	6	Newsletter Recipient Database	M6
*Refer to Section 2 of this report for further information about each dataset.				

For each dataset it is stated if and how they will be shared or licensed; what standards will be followed and how datasets are stored.

1. Introduction

1.1 Data Pitch: brief overview

Data Pitch is an open innovation project that brings together corporates and public sector organisations that have data, with startups and SMEs working with data. It is centred around a competition calling for innovative solutions to challenges set by the data-owning organisations and challenges developed by expert consultation; and an accelerator programme to help startups and SME develop solutions to meet these challenges.

Data Pitch manages the overall programme, organises the competition and selection process, funds the best ideas, and helps the winners deliver their innovative solutions.

Data Pitch, therefore, is concerned with two kinds of datasets: (1) those that are shared by data providers; and (2) those that are generated or collected in the commission of the project over its duration. This Data Management Plan (DMP) is concerned with the latter type (2), and addresses:

- How datasets will be exploited/shared/licensed. For those that cannot be shared, the reasons why are explained.
- Which standards are followed for publishing datasets.
- Which strategies are used for curation and archiving of datasets.

1.2 Objective of the Data Management Plan

This report - Data Management Plan v2 - provides an update to the first DMP delivered in M6 by: (i) reviewing and (if necessary) amending the information about the datasets recorded in the first version of the DMP; and (ii) adding information about any additional datasets.

The following table lists the 17 datasets that have been/will be generated/collected over the course of the Data Pitch programme (note that the four datasets highlighted in blue are new additions to the DMP):

Overview of datasets generated/collected over the course of the Data Pitch programme*				
	Dataset reference	Relevant work package(s)	Dataset Name	First recorded in DMP
1	DS-2A	2	Statistics on Usage of Data and Infrastructure	M6
2	DS-3A	3	Data Providers Database	M6
3	DS-3B	3	Data Providers Legal and Technical Submissions	M6
4	DS-3C	3	Data Providers Challenge Templates	M6
5	DS-3D	3	Challenge Consultation	M6
6	DS-3E	3	Data Provider Contracts	M6

7	DS-3F	3	Data Providers' Metadata	M6
8	DS-4A	4	General Statistics on Call for Applications	M6
9	DS-4B	4	Database of Submissions	M6
10	DS-4C	4	Non-Successful Applicants' Email Addresses	M19
11	DS-4D	4	Evaluation and Interview Results	M6
12	DS-4E	4	SME Contracts, Declarations of Honour, Ethics Statement and Other Signed Manuscripts	M6
13	DS-4F	4 and 5	Records of Self-Supplied Data	M19
14	DS-5A	5	Statistics on Start-up Acceleration	M6
15	DS-5B	5	SME Accelerator Working Documents	M19
16	DS-5C	5 and 6	Accelerator Training Materials	M19
17	DS-6A	6	Newsletter Recipient Database	M6
*Refer to Section 2 of this report for further information about each dataset.				

1.3 Personal data

There are three types of personal data collected by Data Pitch:

1. **Contact information** – i.e. names, email addresses and phone numbers – in order to communicate with (potential) data providers and applicants. The legal basis for which are (unless otherwise specified*): (i) the performance of a contract; and (ii) legitimate interests – to identify potential data providers.
2. **Images of individuals involved with Data Pitch** – It will be necessary for Data Pitch's legitimate business interests to use these images to promote the call and accelerator through social media and other dissemination channels. See Dataset DS-5C (Accelerator Training Materials) for further information.
3. **Videos of Data Pitch activities** – The start-ups agree to be interviewed and included in videos – such as:
 - a. Two content productions – (i) Data Pitch Kick Off Video and (ii) Demonstration Day Video – that are available on the Data Pitch Youtube Channel. It will be necessary for Data Pitch's legitimate business interests to use these videos to promote the call and

accelerator.

- b. Individual pitch recordings that are stored only on Google Drive. It will be necessary for Data Pitch's legitimate business interests to use these pitch recordings for training purposes.

See Dataset DS-5C (Accelerator Training Materials) for further information.

*Note that in the case of Dataset DS-4C (Non-Successful Applicant's Email Addresses) the legal basis is consent for the following purposes:

- 1. Marketing communications – unless the following applies:**
 - a. An applicant has previously received marketing communications from Data Pitch – it will be necessary for Data Pitch's legitimate business interests to ensure the applicant continues to receive communications.
 - b. An applicant has specifically asked Data Pitch to provide marketing communications – it will be necessary for Data Pitch's legitimate business interests to ensure the applicant is provided with requested communications.
- 2. Where a non-successful applicant applied to a specific Data Provider Challenge, the contact details of the non-successful applicant will be provided to the corresponding Data Provider.**

2. List of Datasets

2.1 Data Providers Database

Dataset Reference	DS-3A
Relevant Work Package	WP3 Data and data providers' liaison
Type	Collected
Origin	Project partners
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~50Mb)
Description	All companies approached for and committed to data sharing in Data Pitch.
Useful to	European Commission, project partners, future Horizon2020 projects and future initiatives concerning start-up incubation and data sharing.
Integration and Reuse possibilities	None
Standards	Google Spreadsheet
Data Sharing Policy	Internal.
Archiving and Storage	This dataset will be stored in the project Google Drive and destroyed at the end of the preservation time. This includes the destruction of any copies on Google Drive and personal computers.
Preservation Time	Two years beyond the end of the project, according to D7.3.

Additional preservation cost	None.
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2.2 Data Providers Legal and Technical Submissions

Dataset Reference	DS-3B
Relevant Work Package	WP3 Data and data providers' liaison
Type	Collected
Origin	Requested by Data Pitch for due diligence on data sets
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~100Mb)
Description	Detailed description of legal and technical status of data sets shared by data providers, including potential privacy and GDPR issues and other legal issues.
Useful to	Data Pitch legal team in ensuring data is correctly provided as well as in creating the Legal and Privacy Toolkit (Deliverable 3.1)
Integration and Reuse possibilities	None
Standards	Email, pdf.
Data Sharing Policy	Not to be shared. The status of their data belongs to data providers.
Archiving and Storage	This dataset will be stored in the project Google Drive and destroyed at the end of the preservation time. This includes the destruction of any copies on Google Drive and personal computers.
Preservation Time	Project's lifetime.
Additional preservation cost	None.

2.3 Data Providers Challenge Templates

Dataset Reference	DS-3C
Relevant Work Package	WP3 Data and data providers' liaison
Type	Collected
Origin	Data Pitch website
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~100Mb)
Description	The challenge database contains the text describing challenges and relevant datasets as defined by data providers.
Useful to	The Data Pitch consortium in setting the challenges for the competitive call.
Integration and Reuse possibilities	Other innovation challenges; data owners considering which are the most valuable datasets to open.
Standards	Email, docs, pdf.
Data Sharing Policy	The challenges will be open and available in the Competitive Call. Demographic statistics will be published on the Data Pitch website.
Archiving and Storage	This dataset will be stored in the project Google Drive and destroyed at the end of the preservation time. This includes the destruction of any copies on Google Drive and personal computers.
Preservation Time	Two years beyond the end of the project, according to D7.3.

Additional preservation cost	None
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2.4 Challenge Consultation

Dataset Reference	DS-3D
Relevant Work Package	WP3 Data and data providers' liaison
Type	Collected
Origin	Data Pitch website
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~100Mb)
Description	The consultation database contains the complete answers to the Data Pitch challenge public consultation.
Useful to	The Data Pitch consortium in setting the challenges for the competitive call.
Integration and Reuse possibilities	Other innovation challenges; data owners considering which are the most valuable datasets to open.
Standards	Google doc spreadsheet.
Data Sharing Policy	The suggested challenges will be open and available in the Competitive Call. Demographic statistics will be published on the Data Pitch website.
Archiving and Storage	This dataset will be stored in the project Google Drive and destroyed at the end of the preservation time. This includes the destruction of any copies on Google Drive and personal computers.
Preservation Time	Two years beyond the end of the project, according to D7.3.

Additional preservation cost	None
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2.5 General Statistics on Call for Applications

Dataset Reference	DS-4A
Relevant Work Package	WP4 Competitive call
Type	Collected
Origin	Submission Platform
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~10Mb)
Description	<p>Statistics on the Call, per evaluation round and consolidated, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of applications ● Number of applicants ● Size in employees of applicants ● Number of shortlisted applications ● Number of successful applications ● Number of projects successfully completed. <p>For each of the above indicators, per country numbers will be available.</p>
Useful to	<p>Incubation initiatives and decision makers on start-up acceleration policies who can use these datasets to improve their work.</p> <p>Data owners, publishers and users seeking statistical evidence of interest in utilisation of third party datasets for innovation by startups and SMEs.</p>

<p>Integration and Reuse possibilities</p>	<p>Integration with statistics from other data innovation incubation initiatives may provide insight on the best funding/grant model.</p> <p>Comparison with incubation initiatives on other domains can provide insight on the net value of each domain and the dynamism of the business ecosystem for each domain.</p> <p>Provision of evidence for supporting data freeflow initiatives.</p>
<p>Standards</p>	<p>Spreadsheets on .xls and .odt formats, plus .csv files</p>
<p>Data Sharing Policy</p>	<p>Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.</p>
<p>Archiving and Storage</p>	<p>Stored in the Google Drive of the project and published on the project's website.</p> <p>Destruction at the end of preservation time will include any personal computers where the project Google Drive was downloaded.</p>
<p>Preservation Time</p>	<p>Two years beyond the end of the project, according to D7.3.</p>
<p>Additional preservation cost</p>	<p>None.</p>

2.6 Database of submissions

Dataset Reference	DS-4B
Relevant Work Package	WP4 Competitive call
Type	Collected
Origin	Submission Platform - F6S
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~100Mb)
Description	The database of submissions contains the full information of all the applications submitted to Data Pitch.
Useful to	Evaluators, data providers and mentors within Data Pitch, researchers within the Data Pitch consortium. Other incubators who may be interested in inviting applicants to join.
Integration and Reuse possibilities	Academic research on open innovation, data business models and similar.
Standards	Backend of the submission platform.
Data Sharing Policy	Not to be shared. The intellectual property of the ideas outlined in the submissions belong to the applicants. Only the statistics for dataset DS-2A will be collected.
Archiving and Storage	During the project's lifetime, it will be stored in the submission platform. Afterwards, it will be destroyed to guarantee confidentiality.
Preservation Time	Project's lifetime.
Additional preservation cost	None.

2.7 Evaluation and interview results

Dataset Reference	DS-4D
Relevant Work Package	WP4 Competitive call
Type	Generated
Origin	Submission Platform, interview notes
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~50Mb)
Description	Unsuccessful applications that are not short-listed will receive an email with the comments of the evaluators. Unsuccessful applications that were shortlisted may receive more detailed comments agreed by both evaluators.
Useful to	Evaluators and applicants
Integration and Reuse possibilities	None
Standards	Spreadsheet, word processed documents and email.
Data Sharing Policy	Not to be shared. Comments belong to the applicants, as they reveal details about their ideas.
Archiving and Storage	This dataset will be stored in the project Google Drive and destroyed at the end of the preservation time. This includes the destruction of any copies on Google Drive and personal computers.
Preservation Time	Project's lifetime.
Additional preservation cost	None.

2.8 Non-successful applicants' email addresses

Dataset reference	DS-4C
Relevant Work Package	WP4 Competitive call
Type	Collected
Origin	Non-successful applicants to Data Pitch call
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~10Mb)
Description	A list of email addresses of non-successful applicants. Non-successful applicants will be given the option of providing their email addresses to Data Pitch for the uses specified in the box below. Non-successful applicants will have the possibility to withdraw their consent through an opt-out email.
Useful to	<p>The Data Pitch Consortium in order to carry out the following activities during the course of the project:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Data Pitch will use this dataset to email non-successful applicants about other opportunities, challenges and accelerators. (2) Data Pitch will use this dataset to invite non-successful applicants to events. (3) Where a non-successful applicant applied to a specific Data Provider Challenge, the contact details of the non-successful applicant will be provided to the corresponding Data Provider.
Integration and re-use possibilities	None
Standards	Spreadsheets on .xls and .odt formats, plus .csv files and backend of the submission platform.
Data Sharing Policy	Internal
Archiving and Storage	This dataset will be stored in the project Google Drive and destroyed at the end of the preservation time. This includes the destruction of

	<p>any copies on Google Drive and personal computers.</p> <p>During the project's lifetime, it will also be stored in the submission platform. Afterwards, it will be destroyed to guarantee confidentiality.</p>
Preservation Time	Project's lifetime.
Additional Preservation Cost	None

2.9 Records of self-supplied data

Dataset reference	DS-4F
Relevant Work Packages	WP4 Competitive call WP5 Incubator
Type	Collected
Origin	Successful applicants' 'Record of information about self-supplied data' form
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~100Mb)
Description	The self-supplied data records describe the number, nature and source of each self-supplied dataset that successful applicants intend - and have permission - to analyse as part of their challenge.
Useful to	Data Pitch legal team in ensuring data is correctly provided as well as in creating the Legal and Privacy Toolkit (Deliverable 3.1)
Integration and re-use possibilities	None
Standards	Word and Google documents.
Data Sharing Policy	Internal
Archiving and Storage	This dataset will be stored in the project Google Drive and destroyed at the end of the preservation time. This includes the destruction of any copies on Google Drive and personal computers.

Preservation Time	Project's lifetime.
Additional Preservation Cost	None

2.10 Statistics on startup acceleration

Dataset Reference	DS-5A
Relevant Work Package	WP5 Incubator
Type	Collected
Origin	Internal reports
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~10Mb)
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● From the tracking activity, publish aggregate data about the level of satisfaction with the programme. ● Access statistics of online training materials: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ number of users ○ the most and less consulted. ● Success rate of startups achieving milestones. (achieved milestones / total milestones). ● Percentage of successfully completed projects. ● Count of mentors split by sector and level of satisfaction of the mentorship
Useful to	<p>Other data acceleration initiatives.</p> <p>Reference point for learning about best practices.</p>
Integration and Reuse possibilities	With similar data from other incubation initiatives.

Standards	.xls, .odt and .csv . This dataset will also be published in .pdf format as part of deliverable 6.5
Data Sharing Policy	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License .
Archiving and Storage	This dataset will be stored in the project Google Drive and destroyed at the end of the preservation time. This includes the destruction of any copies on Google Drive and personal computers.
Preservation Time	Two years beyond the end of the project, according to D7.3.
Additional preservation cost	None.

2.11 Statistics on usage of data and computing infrastructure.

Dataset Reference	DS-2A
Relevant Work Package	WP2 Data experimentation facilities
Type	Collected
Origin	Data and Computing Infrastructure
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~10Mb)
Description	<p>For the selected projects, statistics will be collected on:</p> <p>How many data providers choose to use Data Pitch infrastructure.</p> <p>How many startups choose to use Data Pitch infrastructure</p> <p>Bugs and Issues with the platform.</p> <p>Which of the tools provided by the consortium the startup is using.</p> <p>Which other (free or paid) tools the project is using.</p> <p>Which datasets the project is using.</p> <p>Which closed, private, shared datasets the project is using.</p>
Useful to	<p>Other data acceleration initiatives.</p> <p>FI-Ware core developers and maintainers.</p> <p>Developers of data sharing toolkits.</p> <p>Dataset providers.</p>
Integration and Reuse possibilities	<p>Assigning each project an URI and linking it to the datasets it uses (dependent on licensing) enables reuse through Linked Data technologies.</p>

Standards	Bugs and issues will be published in the FI-Ware platform. .xls, .odt, .csv and RDF will be used for the rest.
Data Sharing Policy	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.
Archiving and Storage	<p>Bugs and issues will be archived in the platform. The other stats will be collected by the Data Pitch consortium partners and stored in the project's Drive space.</p> <p>At the end of the preservation time this dataset will be destroyed including any copies on the Google Drive or any personal computers.</p>
Preservation Time	Two years beyond the end of the project, according to D7.3.
Additional preservation cost	None.

2.12 Newsletter recipient database

Dataset Reference	DS-6A
Relevant Work Package	WP6 Dissemination, community building, communication
Type	Collected
Origin	Data Pitch Website
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~100Mb)
Description	The database of contact details for all persons and persons representing companies who have requested to be added to the Data Pitch mailing list.
Useful to	Data Pitch communications team, consortium members
Integration and Reuse possibilities	None
Standards	MailChimp and spreadsheet
Data Sharing Policy	Not to be shared.
Archiving and Storage	This dataset will be stored in the project Google Drive and destroyed at the end of the preservation time. This includes the destruction of any copies on Google Drive and personal computers.
Preservation Time	Project's lifetime.
Additional preservation cost	None.

2.13 Data Provider Contracts

Dataset Reference	DS-3E
Relevant Work Package	WP3 Data and data providers' liaison
Type	Collected
Origin	Generated
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~100Mb)
Description	Copy of manuscript signature of contracts executed by parties.
Useful to	Data Pitch consortium members, partner legal teams
Integration and Reuse possibilities	None
Standards	.pdf
Data Sharing Policy	Not to be shared.
Archiving and Storage	Kept with University of Southampton legal department. Counterpart copies kept by external signatories.
Preservation Time	Compliant with parties legal record keeping.
Additional preservation cost	None.

2.14 SME Contracts, Declarations of Honour, Ethics Statement and other signed

manuscripts

Dataset Reference	DS-4E
Relevant Work Package	WP4 Competitive call
Type	Collected
Origin	Data Pitch Website
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~100Mb)
Description	Copy of manuscript signature of contracts executed by parties.
Useful to	Data Pitch consortium members
Integration and Reuse possibilities	None
Standards	.pdf
Data Sharing Policy	Not to be shared.
Archiving and Storage	Kept with University of Southampton legal department. Counterpart copies kept by external signatories.
Preservation Time	Compliant with parties legal record keeping.
Additional preservation cost	None.

2.15 Data Providers' Metadata

Dataset Reference	DS-3F
Relevant Work Package	WP3 Data and data providers' liaison
Type	Acquired
Origin	Data Providers
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~100Mb)
Description	Metadata on data provided by data providers
Useful to	Data Pitch consortium members, SMEs
Integration and Reuse possibilities	None
Standards	.docx, .pdf
Data Sharing Policy	Not to be shared.
Archiving and Storage	Data Pitch Metadata Catalogue on the Dawex platform.
Preservation Time	<p>Duration of project or less, if requested by data owners.</p> <p>According to the project's sustainability strategy set out in D7.3, upon request from a data owner, this information can be preserved up to two years beyond the project.</p>

Additional preservation cost	None.
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2.16 SME Accelerator working documents

Dataset Reference	DS-5B
Relevant Work Package	WP5 Incubator
Type	Collected
Origin	SMEs, accelerator apps like AirTable, Mentornity, internal surveys
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~100Mb)
Description	Includes internal surveys, workplans, budgets, collaborative working documents and mentoring information.
Useful to	WP5
Integration and Reuse possibilities	None
Standards	Word documents, emails, spreadsheets
Data Sharing Policy	Not to be shared.
Archiving and Storage	This dataset will be stored in the project Google Drive, on apps such as AirTable and Mentornity and destroyed at the end of the preservation time. This includes the destruction of any copies on the abovementioned apps, Google Drive and personal computers.
Preservation Time	Project's lifetime.
Additional preservation cost	None.

2.17 Accelerator training materials

Dataset Reference	DS-5C
Relevant Work Packages	WP5 Incubator WP6 Dissemination, community building, communication
Type	Generated
Origin	Data Pitch partners, SMEs and wider data-driven innovation community
Scale (Approx End Volume)	Small (~100Mb)
Description	Training materials on a variety of data-driven innovation and data sharing topics
Useful to	Data Pitch consortium members, wider data-driven innovation community
Integration and Reuse possibilities	Wider training and knowledge sharing
Standards	Slides, videos, word processed documents
Data Sharing Policy	Public
Archiving and Storage	This dataset will be stored in the project Google Drive, and on the Project website, publicly available via our Youtube channel.
Preservation Time	Two years beyond the end of the project, according to D7.3.
Additional preservation cost	None.

